

Evaluation of thermal decomposition of liver tissues from both control and chromium-inoculated chick embryos by thermogravimetric analysis

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The order of reactions and activation energy associated with the thermal decomposition of Cr-inoculated liver tissue and control liver tissue of chick embryo have been obtained by thermogravimetric methods in absence and presence of nitrogen atmosphere. In the temperature range of 25° to about 1100°, the differential thermogram has yielded four distinct peaks for these samples. However, the fourth peak has disappeared in nitrogen atmosphere. The thermal decomposition corresponding to each peak has been analysed and activation energy estimated accordingly. The peak temperature associated with the first peak decreases as the water content in the sample increases. The first and the second peaks correspond to losses of water and protein, respectively. The third and fourth peaks have been identified for mucopolysaccharide and due to oxidation in presence of air at high temperature, respectively. These decomposition behaviours are similar to the collagen content in liver tissues.

Over the years enormous progress has been made in the understanding of the physical roles and the nature of solid fibrous collagen in connective tissue using various methods. Earlier, we investigated the micelle formation on various collagen solutions and also highlighted the interaction of different ionic and nonionic surfactant micelles with these collagens¹. The stability of the collagen structures, conformations, geometry, hydration and thermodynamic studies had been made in various surfactants and urea environments¹. However, to the best of our knowledge, the activation energy associated with the thermal decomposition of liver tissues obtained from chick embryos has not been examined so far. Therefore, in this report, the activation energy associated with the thermal decomposition of liver tissues from both control and chromium inoculated chick embryos by thermogravimetric analysis has been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

A primary weight-loss for control liver tissue and Cr-inoculated liver tissue as a function of temperature is shown in Fig. 1. There were four temperatures at which the onset of thermal degradation occurred. Since the onset temperatures of degradation are not clear from the primary weight-loss curve, differential thermograms are also presented in Fig. 1 (at the bottom). Four minimum inflection points are observed at 200, 425, 550 and 770° in a differential thermogram of control liver tissue, whereas for test sample (Cr-inoculated) the corresponding minimum inflection points are at 205, 320, 425 and 700°. Four maximum peak points are also observed at 165, 348, 535 and

Fig. 1. (a) Weight-loss of liver tissue of chick embryo : Cr-inoculated (T and T') and control (C and C'), heated at atmospheric pressure, heating rate 20°/min. (b) Differential thermogram of the above test (T and T') and control (C and C') samples. The primes T' and C' represent that the experiments were performed in N₂ atmosphere.

790° in the above differential thermogram of control sample, whereas the corresponding peak points for test sample are at 150, 300, 345 and 730°. That means, the maximum as well as minimum inflection points occurred always at lower temperatures in test sample as compared to control samples except at the first peak. In the first peak, the temperature range is more or less equal for both the samples. It is interesting to note that the first and the second peak overlapped each other for test sample, how-

ever, this behaviour was not observed in control sample. Complete decomposition occurred at about 950° for test samples compared to 1050° for control sample.

Table 1. Order of reactions and activation parameters of Cr-inoculated liver tissue of chick embryo and the control samples, corresponding to different compositions in absence and presence of N₂ atmosphere*

Phase	Temp.range (°C)		E _a (kcal mol ⁻¹)		n	
	Control	Test	Control	Test	Control	Test
1	50-270 (55-275)	50-260 (55-265)	4.5 ± 0.2 (4.6 ± 0.2)	4.4 ± 0.2 (4.5 ± 0.2)	1.3 ± 0.3 (1.2 ± 0.2)	1.25 ± 0.3 (1.3 ± 0.3)
2	270-460 (275-465)	260-460 (270-465)	12.5 ± 0.4 (13.0 ± 0.3)	12.0 ± 0.5 (12.5 ± 0.2)	1.95 ± 0.08 (1.85 ± 0.1)	1.92 ± 0.05 (1.8 ± 0.1)
3	460-720 (470-750)	460-700 (470-740)	7.0 ± 0.5 (9.2 ± 0.4)	8.9 ± 0.5 (12.5 ± 0.3)	1.75 ± 0.2 (1.6 ± 0.3)	1.8 ± 0.3 (1.7 ± 0.2)
4	720-1000	700-900	14.5 ± 0.4	16.5 ± 0.5	1.9 ± 0.2	1.95 ± 0.4

*Values in parenthesis were obtained in N₂ atmosphere.

The order of reaction (*n*) is obtained from the slope of the plot of dC/dt against $(1-C)$ on a logarithmic scale. Such graphical representations are not shown here, but the *n* value obtained corresponding to various peaks is shown in Table 1. The activation energy associated with various peaks is estimated from the plot of $\ln(1-C)$ vs $(1/T)$ using the Doyle equation².

$$\ln(1-C) = -2.315 (A/B) + 0.4567 (A/B) \cdot (E_a/R) \cdot (1/T) \quad (1)$$

The plot of $\ln(1-C)$ vs $1/T$ is shown in Fig. 2 and the activation energy obtained from this plot is depicted in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln(1-C)$ vs $1/T$ where 1, 2, 3 and 4 refer to first, second, third and fourth phases, respectively : (o) control, scale-I and (●) test, scale-II.

Like collagen, there is a sizable amount of water in the tissue in addition to other residues (primarily proline and hydroxyproline). The bonding of this water to peptide chains has already been investigated³. The possible bonding sites of water are mostly at the C=O and N-H group of the chains. Of course, a water-water bond is also possible if water is in plentiful. There is no available thermal activation data of Cr-inoculated liver tissue of chick embryo in the literature, to our knowledge. However, collagen em-

bedded in bone⁴ and dentin^{5,6} has been analysed by thermogravimetric analysis. The present authors found four peaks in the differential thermogram of bone and dentin. In our present investigation, we have also found four peaks in the differential thermogram of Cr-inoculated liver tissue of chick embryo and its control (i.e. in absence of Cr-inoculation) in absence of N₂ atmosphere. The four regions corresponding to the four peaks have also been obtained in the plot of $\ln(1-C)$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 2). The first and the second peaks correspond to losses of water and protein, respectively. We can classify water in the liver tissue into two categories : adsorbed water and bound water. Weight-loss upto the end of the first peak is about 20 and 17% for control and test samples, respectively. Since the adsorbed water is 9.5 and 9%, the rest of the weight 10.5 and 8% should be bound water for control and test samples, respectively. The activation process associated with the second peak would be related to the breaking of the amide link formed between the amino acid residues to establish the polypeptide chains. One of the characteristics of a polypeptide chain is its high melting temperature which has also been observed here for liver tissue of chick embryo. The activation energy of about 12.5 kcal mol⁻¹ is lower than that of some polypeptide chains in the collagen⁴ evaluated so far. There is no appreciable change in activation energy in the test sample compared to the control as far as first and second phase regions are concerned. However, some appreciable difference in activation energy (Table 1) in the third and fourth phase regions indicates that the thermal stability of Cr-inoculated liver tissue of chick embryo is greater than that of control sample. This has been further evidenced by aggregating nature in the Cr-containing systems⁷. It has also been seen that the liver tissue of chick embryo contains a few percent (~5%) of mucopolysaccharide and some Ca content. Therefore, we had run a thermogravimetric analysis using pure mucopolysaccharide which gave a peak at ~500-600°. Such a DTG curve is not shown here. Therefore, the results indicate that the mucopolysaccharide component contributes in forming the third peak together with other remaining residues that break into smaller subunits at higher temperatures. The fourth peak is similar to the dentinal carbonate phase⁵ and is due to the oxidation in presence of air. This fourth peak was not observed when the samples were run in N₂ atmosphere (Fig. 1). It is interesting to note that all the four peaks are also obtained for various collagen fibers under similar conditions and the E_a values corresponding to 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th peaks are 5.0, 14.5, 10 and 20 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. These possibilities also exist in the liver tissue sample of chick embryo. The calculated activation energy associated with various phase regions are in good agreement with viscosity derived and differential scanning calorimetric results⁸.

Experimental

Liver tissue sample was removed from 18-day old chick embryos which was inoculated with LD₅₀ dose of K₂Cr₂O₇ on the 10th day of incubation (called Test sample). Liver tissue samples taken from chick embryos that were inoculated with physiological saline served as controls. Careful attention was given so that the samples did not get denatured during these preparations. The tissue samples were lyophilized, dessicated and weighed before loading into the thermogravimetric analyser.

A Du Pont 951 thermogravimetric analyser was used. The experiments were performed under normal atmospheric pressure with a heating rate of 20°/min in absence and presence of N₂ atmosphere.

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